

The Influence of Continuing Professional Teacher Development on the Quality of Teaching and Learning in South African Schools

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ABSTRACT

This research explored how continuing professional teacher development (CPTD) can enhance the quality of teaching and learning in South African schools. CPTD activities can nurture a learning environment that inspires teachers to update their knowledge and skills. The study adopted Albert Bandura's (1977) social learning theory to explore the reasons why beginner and experienced teachers do not engage in CPTD programmes and upgrade their qualifications to improve their knowledge. It adopted the interpretivist paradigm and qualitative methodology to probe how CPTD influences the quality of teaching and learning. Altogether, 30 participants, comprising six principals, eight departmental heads, 12 teachers, and four union site stewards, were selected from nine primary schools in four circuits within the Vhembe East District in Limpopo Province. Structured interviews, direct observations, and document analysis were employed to gather firsthand information from participants on how CPTD can improve the quality of education for learners. The findings revealed that the South African education system is comparatively low due to teachers' inadequate instructional skills, low motivation, and unsatisfactory salary levels. Hence, there is a need for teachers to update their content and pedagogical knowledge to improve the standard of teaching and learning in schools. The study further revealed that CPTD success depends mainly on teachers' intrinsic motivation and readiness for self-development, more so than on external factors such as incentives and pressure from the employer. Despite some weaknesses, CPTD remains vital for improving the quality of education in South Africa. Therefore, teachers should engage in robust continuous professional development (CPD) programmes to improve teaching and learning standards in schools.

Keywords: Continuing professional teacher development, discipline, incentives, learning resources, motivation, physical infrastructure, teaching and learning

INTRODUCTION

South Africa is experiencing the deterioration of teaching and learning standards in schools because of multiple factors such as demoralised teachers, a lack of leadership support, inadequate teaching and learning resources, a lack of CPTD practices, redeployment and rationalisation of teachers (R&R), the inability to manage learners' problems, dilapidated infrastructure, difficulties in managing the curriculum, a lack of teacher incentives and many other challenges. Fredriksson (2004) and Zhang et al. (2022) agree that if employers and school managers can address issues such as salaries, teacher education, school-level working conditions, the quality of teaching and learning will improve. However, a study conducted in

Nigeria by Enwezor (2020) found that while higher salaries and promotions may satisfy teachers, they do not encourage them to work harder or improve learners' achievement.

As is the case with many other professions, teaching is a field that is constantly evolving. Hence, teachers should not only depend on their initial pre-service training knowledge, skills, and experience to manage the current developments in education. Since CPTD extends beyond formal education training, it provides new ways to enhance teaching, adapt to classroom changes, and stay up to date with the latest advances in education. CPTD entails teachers' ongoing learning and development throughout their careers to enhance their effectiveness, educational quality, learner achievement, and school effectiveness (Adu et al., 2023; Asmare, 2025). Providing teachers with opportunities to learn and grow professionally makes them feel valued and appreciated, enhances their professional competence, and increases their job satisfaction and work commitment (Adu et al., 2023; Asmare, 2025; Lafferty et al., 2023).

CPTD practices equip teachers with practical methods to manage classroom dynamics and conflicts, ensuring a safe and tranquil learning environment. The approach further provides teachers with strategies to maintain discipline in the classrooms while fostering a positive atmosphere conducive to effective teaching and learning. Well-designed CPTD models enable teachers to connect and interact with colleagues, mentors, and experts from similar or different educational fields, sharing resources, exchanging ideas, and collaborating on challenging subjects or topics in a way that enhances teaching and learning in their respective schools. As the educational terrain continues to evolve, embracing teacher continuous professional development (CPD) will not only enhance teaching quality and learner performance but also inspire a lifelong passion for learning among teachers, ultimately benefiting learners and the broader education system.

Educational leaders are expected to help teachers identify their own needs and create opportunities for them to attend CPD programmes on school management, which can lead to future promotions. CPTD assists teachers in managing their time and staying organised to deliver quality education to all learners (Adu et al., 2023; Lafferty et al., 2023; Steyn & Van Niekerk, 2008). Another advantage of this practice is that teachers can dedicate more time to classroom teaching than to administrative tasks. It enables teachers to feel valued by the organisation and seek ways to improve their skills, knowledge, and expertise, transform their attitudes towards the job, and adjust their behaviour patterns within the organisation.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

In South Africa, low teacher morale, poor working relationships between teachers and school management teams, tensions between teachers and the employer (Department of Basic Education [DBE]), classroom management and learner discipline challenges, bad conditions of services, deteriorating physical infrastructure, inadequate teaching and learning resources, little or no CPTD practices are some of the contextual deficiencies that threaten education quality in schools. A lack of DBE support for teachers on critical areas of teacher development such as curriculum management, new methods of instruction and learning, new modes of learner assessment, digital collaboration, the implementation of Quality Management System's (QMS) three programmes: Whole School Evaluation (WSE), Developmental Appraisal System (DAS) and CPTD; change management; departmental policies and many others, have left many teachers with no alternatives to take other than to exit the teaching profession. This gross

negligence by the DBE has forced many teachers to abandon their interest and motivation to upgrade and improve their qualifications and areas of specialisation. Despite all these challenges, teachers are expected to be fully accountable to their employers and parents for learners' successful learning. They must also be prepared to undergo professional development programmes for their personal career growth and improvement of learner achievement.

The introduction of DAS by the employer aims to reward teachers by providing a one percent salary progression annually. However, it overlooks the well-intended outcomes outlined in the Education Labor Relations Council (ELRC) Collective Agreement No.8 of 2003, which include peaceful dispute resolution between trade unions and the state as the employer. The information contained in the QMS policy documents is valuable for personal professional growth. However, teachers and principals either file and forget or neglect these documents, undermining their relevance and value. QMS has yielded very little or no benefit and does not outline the mechanisms for improving teaching and learning in schools. According to Mukhavhuli (2017), no one claims to be an authority on these aspects of policy, and the value they add to teaching and learning is still an unanswered puzzle. The employer has substituted the salary notch increase system with a cash bonus reward for every additional qualification obtained by teachers (DBE, 2025; EEA NO, 76 of 1998, 2003: C-79). The implementation of this practice implies that the employer does not reward teachers with a salary notch increase for every Relative Education Qualification Value (REQV) they acquire. Instead, they will receive a one-time payment in the form of a cash bonus equal to 10% of the entry notch of the REQV (DBE, 2025).

To avoid being held accountable by employers, parents, and other stakeholders interested in the learners' education and achievement, principals and teachers disproportionately focus on the exit grade (Grade 12), as it attracts significant public attention to the results obtained in the high-stakes matric (national) examinations. In the process, lower grades are grossly neglected, compromising the quality of teaching and learning in schools. Sadly, teachers are always preoccupied with unnecessary departmental meetings and paper administration. To project a positive public image, schools have reduced teaching and learning to intensive preparation of Grade 12 learners for examinations, practising on old examination papers, and marking memos. The drill-and-practice technique defeats the purpose of education and erodes the quality of knowledge and skills that teachers and learners acquire. While Grade 12 results appear to be statistically sound, they are qualitatively poor, as learners produce a very narrow scope of knowledge and skills and lack problem-solving and higher-order skills due to superficial teaching (Hlongwane & Lekhetho, 2025; Mlachila & Moeletsi, 2019; Styron & Styron, 2012).

The factors stated above can potentially lower the quality of teaching and learning in schools. The introduction of CPTD practices, with their intended outcomes outlined in QMS documents, could enhance teachers' knowledge and skills in teaching and learning in schools. Teachers are engaged in various teacher development programmes to improve the deteriorating quality of teaching and student learning in schools.

1. Research Question

To clarify the research problem stated above, the main question this study sought to address is as follows: How can continuing professional teacher development improve the declining quality of education in South African schools?

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Bell and Waters (2018) define a theoretical framework as an explanatory device that graphically or narratively explains the main aspects to be studied, the key factors, constructs, or variables, and the presumed relationships among them. Kivunja and Kuyini (2017) describe the theoretical framework as a structure that summarises concepts and theories developed by the researcher from previously tested and published knowledge to support their study.

Bandura's (1977) social learning theory is relevant to guide this article that explores the influence of CPTD on the quality of teaching and learning in South African schools (Swartz et al., 2016). This theory posits that learning and motivation are influenced by individuals' thoughts and beliefs (self-efficacy) and their observations of others' behaviours (Jones & George, 2016; Mayes, 2015). The theory assumes that learning occurs through observation, also known as vicarious learning. Vicarious learning is a powerful source of motivation in many jobs where people learn to perform functional behaviours by watching or observing others (Jones & George, 2016; Park & Puranam, 2023). This learning occurs when a person (the learner) becomes motivated to perform a behaviour by watching another person (the model) perform the behaviour and being positively reinforced for doing so. Weiten (2007) and Robbins and Decenzo (2004) share the collective view that reinforcement (praise) is a critical determinant of behaviour and influences performance rather than learning per se. Bandura asserts that people are more likely to be motivated to imitate the behaviour of people (models) who are competent, have high status, and receive attractive reinforcers (Jones & George, 2016; Park & Puranam, 2023).

In a school setting, teachers can observe the skills or behaviours demonstrated by their models, such as the heads of departments (HODs), deputy principals, or principals. The teacher can choose the desired skills or behaviours and formulate their own. This model of learning motivates teachers who aspire to leadership positions by emulating the behaviours of those who occupy positions of trust, authority, and influence. Based on Bandura's social learning theory, teachers can become intrinsically motivated when they are invited to attend functions such as school award ceremonies, circuit award ceremonies, district award ceremonies, or university graduation ceremonies. When they observe others receiving awards such as merit certificates, money, laptops, trophies, diplomas, and degree certificates, as well as scholarships and bursaries, teachers can become intrinsically motivated and experience vicarious reinforcement. Vicarious reinforcement occurs when one person observes another (a model) behave in a certain way. In turn, the observer emulates the model's behaviour that they consider desirable (Arrastia-Chisholm et al., 2020). These incentives can stimulate teachers to work very hard to receive the awards.

Some teachers may enrol for further qualifications with the ambition of occupying high managerial positions. Steyn and Van Niekerk (2018) consider a public award appropriate when someone has performed exceptionally well, particularly if such a performance has benefited the entire staff or all learners. They caution that school authorities or an organising agency must plan public recognition of teachers carefully, as such an action can cause dissatisfaction among teachers who have not been recognised.

According to Macruf et al. (2020), incentive provision is a trigger tool for improving the quality of teachers' performance and service. If teachers are given incentives, they can exert extra effort in activities such as assigning additional homework to learners, administering classwork

tests and practice tests, and conducting extra classes after school (Nyinamasiko, 2021). She maintains that employers and local authorities should offer extrinsic rewards, such as presents, promotions, salary increments, and cash bonuses, to teachers who have demonstrated outstanding performance or upon completing a particular task (Nyinamasiko, 2021). She maintains that the most common and understood incentive workers want is money.

Self-reinforcement in observational learning can drive both teachers and learners to improve their behaviours in schools. According to Swartz et al. (2018), Bandura believes that the process of self-reinforcement through observational learning provides people with self-direction by dictating which behaviours people can maintain, improve, or discontinue. In a classroom context, for instance, observational learning promotes the personal and professional growth of teachers, ultimately enhancing the quality of teaching and learning effectiveness. Teachers typically feel highly motivated to attend the formal CPTD programmes designed by their employer, such as subject workshops, leadership seminars, visiting other schools, and attending open lectures facilitated by academics and other experts. By participating in formal programmes stated above, teachers can equip themselves with new content knowledge, skills, and expertise to enhance the quality of teaching and learning for learners.

In a school situation, teachers can be motivated to imitate the behaviour of a model, such as a principal who is always punctual for work every day. In the same vein, learners can be motivated to adopt a positive behaviour from a model, such as a music teacher who excels in dancing or singing during the music period. Through observational learning, such learners may develop an interest in pursuing music as a career or become music teachers. This type of learning occurs through observing the behaviour of others by noting the behavioural consequences of those being observed (Mayes, 2015; Rodriguez Buritica et al., 2024). In a classroom context, music teachers may represent models (musicians) as individual learners who love music may observe and emulate their behaviours.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research inquiry investigated the impact of continuing professional development on the quality of teaching and learning in Vhembe East District schools in Limpopo Province. It investigated how teachers can be engaged in various CPTD programmes to equip and update them with new skills and knowledge, thereby enhancing classroom instruction and student learning. The study adopted a qualitative approach, focusing on participants' meanings and interpretations as expressed in their responses. The researcher visited the participants in their natural settings, interacted with them personally, and invited them to share their experiences of professional development in their schools (Teherani et al., 2015). The qualitative approach enabled the researcher to conduct interviews with principals, HODs, teachers, and the union site stewards in their respective schools, collecting data on how the employer and school management could engage teachers in CPTD practices to enhance the quality of teaching and learning in the classroom. Specifically, the researcher employed structured interviews, document analysis of textual sources, and direct observation to collect data (Gill et al., 2008; Taherdoost, 2021).

The researcher (interviewer) collected data through interviews with participants to gather their views, ideas, experiences, beliefs, and opinions about CPTD programmes (Maree, 2020; Taherdoost, 2021). In line with the structured interview employed, the researcher developed questions in advance and ensured that all participants received the same questions in the same

order (Gill et al., 2008; Punch & Oancea, 2014). The participants were assured that they were free to express their own opinions, insights, experiences, and beliefs in response to the interview questions without any influence from the interviewer or the interview process. The researcher recorded the field accounts of what the participants reported hearing, touching, seeing, or witnessing with their own eyes in the notebook in a pre-planned and controlled manner.

The researcher further consulted documentary sources to gather information. He requested permission from the Limpopo Department of Education (LDE) and circuit managers to visit principals, HODs, and teachers at selected schools to access key documents that were central to the research study. These included the documents related to the three components of QMS (WSE, DAS, and CPTD), the School Governing Body (SGB) Constitution, learners' incident reports, and several others. The principals restricted the researcher from accessing some school documents for security reasons.

The researcher also employed direct observation to gather data on the conditions of the school infrastructure, including classrooms, ablution blocks, libraries, kitchens, and security fences. The participants also indicated the availability or unavailability of teaching and learning resources, as well as other documents relevant to the research topic. Purposive sampling was employed to select research participants, shedding light on the influence of professional teacher development on the quality of education in their schools. When selecting participants, the researcher considered their knowledge of the topic, qualifications, subject specialisation, skills, experience, and designation.

Participants were drawn from nine schools situated in four circuits: Tshinane, Luvuvhu, Mvudi, and Sibasa within the Vhembe East District. All the schools in this study are located in rural communities and categorised as Quintiles 1, 2, and 3, meaning that they are no-fee schools, as they serve communities with low socioeconomic status, as opposed to schools in Quintiles 4 and 5, which are in affluent communities. The sample size consisted of 6 principals, 8 HODs, 12 teachers, and 4 site stewards from teacher unions, totalling 30 participants. The selection of participants was done according to the researcher's knowledge, and they were knowledgeable about the research topic (David & Sutton, 2011). In compliance with the University of South Africa's research ethics policy and the standard operating procedures on ethics risk assessment, the researcher applied for ethical clearance. Subsequently, the UNISA College of Education Ethics Review Committee issued an ethics approval certificate, Ref: 2022/07/06/30903408/18/A.M.

DATA ANALYSIS

This section analyses data collected through different instruments.

1. Structured Interviews

The content analysis was based on data generated from six principals, eight HODs, 12 CSI teachers, and four Union site stewards (USS) from nine schools in Quintiles 1, 2, and 3, across four circuits in the Vhembe East District. Each category of participants was given the same set of questions in the same order (Punch & Oancea, 2014). The researcher created an environment that allowed the participants to provide their own views, opinions, ideas, and experiences on how CPTD influences the quality of teaching and learning in South African schools.

Consistent with a qualitative approach, the researcher employed a thematic analysis to analyse data collected through structured interviews, direct observation, and documentary evidence. He then broke down data into chunks and structured it into *open coding* (classification, marking, and labelling of concepts), *axial coding* (identification of important and general concepts), and, lastly, *selective coding* (generation of main themes/categories and subthemes/categories) (Babbie, 2014; Williams & Moser, 2019). All the themes or categories that shared similar views or relationships based on the main research question and sub-questions were grouped into main themes and subthemes, which eventually determined the ease and simplicity of data presentation, analysis, and interpretation.

The main themes that emerged from the data analysis included critical areas of teacher development, CPTD programmes for enhancing quality education in schools, impediments to CPTD in schools, the creation of CPTD programmes in schools, and motivators (incentives) for attending CPTD programmes. The sub-themes (sub-categories) included knowledge of CPTD concept, the significance of teacher engagement in CPTD initiatives, the competencies of CPTD facilitators, school discipline, classroom management, language gaps, compensation for CPTD attendance, and teacher incentives.

2. Observation of Conditions of Physical Infrastructure

The researcher employed a direct observation technique to collect data on the state of school infrastructure by directly observing the condition of classrooms, laboratories, libraries, ablution facilities or toilets, kitchens, administration offices, and school security fences in the presence of principals, HODs, teachers, and USS. The school leadership and SGBs consented fully to the collection of data through the observation of physical facilities. Accordingly, the researcher captured the fieldnotes with detailed descriptions of what the participants said they saw, witnessed, heard, felt, and experienced in schools.

The researcher observed the physical infrastructure, including teaching and learning resources, in participants' natural settings, namely schools. The researcher also posed some unstructured questions to probe participants' views on the state of physical facilities and the availability of teaching and learning resources, as well as scholastic stationery. Afterwards, the researcher provided a comprehensive description of what he observed and reflected on participants' thoughts and ideas to deduce the meanings of their narratives (Maree, 2020).

The availability of suitable and adequate educational resources has a significant influence on teacher effectiveness, student learning and achievement, school leadership, and school administration. It also emerged that the availability of instructional materials, prescribed books, reference books, and other digital resources enhances curriculum management, the standard of teaching and learning, and learner achievement. The absence or insufficiency of these resources impedes effective teaching and learning, reducing teacher efficiency, educational outcomes, and overall school effectiveness (Mncube et al., 2023).

3. Document Analysis

The researcher employed document analysis to collect data on CPTD and education quality from each of the selected nine schools. Documentary sources that contained relevant information to the research topic included the following: QMS policy documents (SWE, DAS, and CPTD), CAPS documents, the SGB constitution, learners' code of conduct, learners' attendance register, learners' incident report, school diaries, and learners' academic results. The

researcher further accessed documents through libraries, the internet, and appointments with authorisation.

Although cooperative in most aspects, some principals declined to grant access to documents such as staff minutes, teacher union minutes, school diaries, leave registers, and time registers for security and confidentiality reasons, as they contained teachers' personal and sensitive information. They feared that the employer would charge them with gross negligence under the Protection of Personal Information Act (POPIA), which obliges organisations and citizens to protect people's personal information.

An analysis of the documents mentioned above enabled the researcher to determine the influence of CPTD attendance and learners' behaviour on their learning and achievement in the classroom. The researcher obtained all the documents consulted directly from the principals, HODs, and teachers, and thus, they were credible. They provided historical information on why many teachers had lost interest and motivation to upgrade their content knowledge and pedagogical skills, which they had acquired during their formal pre-service training at colleges and universities.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This section discusses research findings derived from different data collection instruments.

1. Discussion of Findings Based on the Interviews

The findings presented in this subsection are based on data generated from interviews conducted with different categories of teachers: six principals, eight departmental heads, 12 teachers, and four union site stewards.

1.1. Critical Areas of Professional Development

The views, opinions, and experiences expressed during the interview sessions revealed that teacher participants had very little or no knowledge of the concept of CPTD. Some participants referred to CPTD as involving extramural activities, managing school finances, attending workshops, and participating in staff meetings. Many teacher participants did not perceive CPTD as a developmental, ongoing programme designed to improve the quality of teaching and learning for teachers, learners, and the entire school. The principals and HODs demonstrated inadequate knowledge and understanding of teacher engagement in CPTD programmes. The findings further revealed that the SMT participants had never engaged teachers in CPTD practices for personal growth and development. Participants' responses highlight an urgent need for the employer (DBE), teacher training institutions (TTIs), and other key stakeholders to introduce compulsory CPD activities for teachers to improve their professional efficiency, student learning, and education quality.

The participants further reported that CPTD programmes would develop teachers' content and pedagogical knowledge, and sharpen their skills in curriculum management, classroom management, and the use of digital technology in schools. To achieve this objective, school principals must help teachers identify their areas for improvement and provide support for personal growth. The participants' views revealed that CPTD facilitators (Curriculum Advisors) had sufficient competencies in content and pedagogical knowledge. The participants were critical of facilitators who seemed to lack content and pedagogical knowledge during their presentations. Although several teachers are equipped with content and pedagogical

knowledge, some are still struggling and require upskilling through rigorous CPD initiatives to improve their instructional competencies.

A lack of learner discipline affects the quality of teaching and learning in schools. Participants perceived schools as toxic environments, rife with learners' violence, bullying, and acts of misconduct. Teachers regard good discipline as a necessary condition for improving student learning and academic results. Poor learner discipline can hinder effective teaching and learning as well as the attainment of intended outcomes.

The participants emphasised that teachers should update their professional knowledge and skills and apply them daily in teaching and learning. Some participants were concerned about learners who had progressed to the next grade without meeting either the pass or progression requirements. They held the DBE accountable for the pass and progression requirements policy that allows underserving learners of specific grades to progress to the next grade through the cohort system. Such learners are typically troublesome in the classroom and can barely read and write for meaning. Teachers always raise concerns about managing learners who have not passed but have just been 'promoted' to the next grade. Hence, the employer or responsible local education authorities must prepare them thoroughly on how to manage problematic and disruptive learners who are struggling academically.

Concerning the language gap in teaching and learning, the findings revealed that the language of learning and teaching (LOLT), which is English First Additional Language, is a significant barrier as it is neither a home language nor a mother tongue to most South African learners, particularly in rural areas. The participants explained that, in most cases, learners know the content but struggle to express it when answering questions due to the language barrier. Hence, the DBE and schools should provide English language support to learners, enriching their linguistic competency, as English is the medium of instruction and central to effective teaching and learning as well as learner success.

The participants viewed CPTD as part of lifelong learning that is integral to teacher efficiency, learner success, and education quality. As such, the employer (mainly the DBE) and school governing bodies should make it mandatory for all teachers to continually improve their professional growth, knowledge, skills, and expertise throughout their teaching careers. Interestingly, teachers showed the desire to continually upgrade their knowledge and qualifications to stay abreast of emerging changes in the field of education.

1.2 Identification of CPTD Programmes

Altogether, 67.7% of the participants interviewed indicated that there were generally no CPTD programmes in schools except for QMS and provider-driven workshops that did not necessarily address teachers' instructional needs. Only 32.3% of the participants demonstrated some knowledge of CPTD programmes available for teachers to engage in lifelong learning and improve their professional competencies, thereby rekindling their love for teaching. They expressed a lack of knowledge about contemporary CPTD methods, including mentoring, peer group exchange, coaching, and e-learning. Teachers must be exposed to current CPTD approaches to prevent knowledge stagnation and a decline in education quality in schools.

1.3 Compensation for Attending CPTD Programmes

Many participants viewed a lack of funds to compensate teachers for attending CPTD programmes as the primary factor contributing to their reluctance to attend and upskill themselves. They disclosed that they require monetary incentives to attend CPTD activities to improve the quality of teaching and learning. The participants further proposed the award of bursaries, laptops, iPads, and trophies as incentives to stimulate CPTD attendance and enhance learner performance.

1.4 Conduct of CPTD Programmes and Incentives for Attending

Most participants suggested that the employer introduce CPTD programmes, support in-service training opportunities, and make participation compulsory for all teachers to gain the knowledge and skills needed for their professional growth and effective teaching and learning. They emphatically stated that CPTD activities must not be conducted during school hours, as such actions would interfere with and reduce instructional time. Most participants supported the idea of making CPTD programmes attendance compulsory for both beginner (novice) and experienced teachers to keep abreast of new developments, content knowledge, instructional methods, and technologies used in education.

Almost all participants suggested that the employer and school authorities should reward teachers for the new knowledge and skills gained through CPTD accordingly, by means of financial incentives such as salary increments, cash bonuses, promotions, bursaries, and laptops to motivate teachers and improve the standard of teaching and learning.

2. Discussion of Findings Based on Observation

The findings in this section are based on data gleaned from the observation schedule.

2.1 Condition of Physical Infrastructure

The school's physical infrastructure, which includes physical facilities, such as buildings, grounds, furniture, and other equipment, creates a conducive learning environment that supports quality teaching and learning. School building facilities should be attractive, have adequate lighting, comfortable seating, and proper service facilities, such as libraries, laboratories, multipurpose rooms, a functional playground, good classrooms, bulletin boards, work areas, and storage space (Motshekga, 2013; Santika et al., 2021). The absence of these facilities undermines efforts to improve the standard of teaching and learning in the classroom and the quality of education. This study aimed to investigate the availability and unavailability of physical facilities, including classrooms, laboratories, libraries, toilets, administration offices, and security fences, as key factors that contribute to a school environment conducive to quality teaching and learning.

The findings from the classroom observation indicated that 78% of the schools participating in the study had dilapidated classrooms that needed urgent renovation or total demolition for the erection of new structures. Some cracks on the walls, broken windows and crumbling roofs made such facilities unconducive to effective teaching and learning. The researcher further observed that while 22% of the schools had usable classrooms, they lacked adequate furniture and desks for all learners.

Regarding laboratory facilities and equipment, direct observation revealed that 89.9% of the schools lacked these facilities. Out of nine participating schools, only one had a laboratory. However, this facility needed urgent renovation, as well as the supply of equipment and materials. A lack of laboratory facilities in schools contributes significantly to low performance in subjects such as physical sciences, life sciences, and agricultural sciences. It is the primary responsibility of the DBE to build laboratories in schools and supply them with the necessary equipment and materials that teachers and learners need to conduct experiments meaningfully.

All categories of participants from the nine schools confirmed that their institutions did not have libraries. These resources are repositories of knowledge that serve as important learning spaces for teachers and learners to learn and develop independent study habits. A library facility supports and encourages literacy and numeracy skills, including reading and writing with meaning and purpose. It allows learners to acquire and master additional information relevant to their assignments, research projects, homework, tests, and other learning activities. A library helps learners to develop the ability to research, think critically, and solve problems independently. It creates a platform for broad and deep reading and enhances teacher performance. The level of teacher quality, in terms of content knowledge, pedagogical expertise, and instructional competence, influences the quality of education offered (Kanya et al., 2021).

While data revealed that toilet facilities were available in all the participating schools, the participants complained about the scarcity of water for flush toilets. Although available, these facilities were not adequate for comfortable use by teachers and learners. Participants from schools with large enrolments indicated that learners often arrived late after breaks due to limited toilet facilities. Hence, the DBE should address the backlog of toilets in many schools as a matter of urgency to create a learner-friendly school environment that promotes teacher productivity and optimises learning.

The participants from nine selected schools confirmed the availability of administration offices. Those from eight schools described the administration offices as good, tidy, and safe for keeping the school's documents, with iron bars in place to protect the doors and windows. They generally perceived the administrative offices as secure and suitable for performing their daily duties effectively. The availability of decent physical facilities, including administration offices, contributes significantly towards improving the quality of teaching and learning in schools.

Direct observation of the security fences revealed that they were present in all the schools. Palisade fencing, brick walls, and barbed wire were erected around the schools to provide adequate safety and security for learners, teachers, and facilities. Additional security measures included the installation of alarms and surveillance devices in some schools. Although most schools had these security facilities, they were still vulnerable to vandalism, theft, violence, and other forms of criminal activity. A lack of these facilities undercuts the quality of teaching and learning, as well as learner discipline in schools.

2.2 Availability of Teaching and Learning Resources

The researcher further observed the availability of teaching and learning resources in the participants' natural settings, namely, schools where teaching and learning activities took place. The researcher also asked participants to express their views about the state of textbooks,

laboratory equipment, chemicals, and computers. The observation of textbook availability revealed that the prescribed textbooks for teachers and learners were inadequate, old, and torn, with many missing pages. Due to their scarcity, learners were forced to share one textbook for individual subjects. If the DBE delays in delivering textbooks to teachers and learners, they may not achieve the expected content coverage and anticipated learning outcomes promptly. The participants' responses indicated that the teachers' and learners' textbooks and teaching resources were inadequate, outdated, and no longer usable due to missing pages. Despite this setback, the mandate of the DBE is to deliver textbooks and scholastic stationery to schools on time. The DBE is also mandated to replace outdated textbooks with new ones promptly to sustain quality teaching and learning in schools.

The observation of science laboratories revealed that 33% of schools had limited laboratory equipment and chemicals. Due to a shortage of proper physical structures, some schools used classrooms as laboratory centres. A lack of laboratory facilities in schools, along with inadequate equipment for conducting experiments, significantly contributes to a high failure rate in learning areas such as physical sciences, life sciences, and agricultural sciences. These challenges underscore an urgent need for the DBE to establish laboratories in all schools and equip them adequately, enabling teachers and learners to conduct experiments efficiently.

When asked about computers, participants confirmed that they were available in their schools for teachers to record, store, and retrieve data as needed. They used them for activities such as recording grades, storing teacher and learner profiles, saving financial data, typing question papers, memoranda, and other official documents. Computers, tablets, and iPads with internet connections offer multiple benefits for teachers and learners, as they provide access to rich, high-quality information related to the curriculum of individual subjects. They empower teachers to work effectively in the classroom and maximise quality learning. Hence, it is essential that the DBE design CPTD programmes to utilise digital technology, enabling teachers to acquire knowledge and skills in using computers, tablets, or iPads.

3. Discussion of Findings Based on Document Study

The researcher employed the documentary sources to collect data on CPTD and education quality from a sample of 30 participants in selected schools. The researcher obtained permission to visit schools in the Vhembe East District from the Limpopo Education Department, circuit managers, and principals. The researcher collected additional data from the libraries, Google search engine, and other websites (Deuscombe, 2017). The participants and the researcher accessed the QMS documents, such as WSE, DAS, and CPTD. Formal documents of learners, such as the learner's code of conduct, the learner's incident report, the school policies, and the SGB constitution, were also made available to collect data from. While the researcher primarily collected data from 30 selected participants, he collected additional data from libraries and the internet. The participants also reported that the QMS documents, such as WSE, DAS, and CPTD, were available in their schools.

3.1 QMS Documents

All the participants reported that all the QMS documents mentioned above were available in their schools. The information in the QMS documents was valuable for improving teachers' personal growth and learner performance. The documents were designed to improve the

effectiveness of schools by enhancing the performance and competence of individual subject teachers.

Principals often locked the documents in cupboards or kept them on the shelves, as most teachers regarded them as a source of additional workload, oppression, and victimisation. Teachers' preconceived ideas highlighted their fear that the QMS documents would be used to reveal their weaknesses and show a lack of confidence in their competencies. This conception characterised the QMS documents as punitive, rather than a job evaluation tool for teachers designed to ultimately improve the standard of teaching and learning and learners' academic performance. In this conception of performance review, teachers agree to complete the QMS and appraisal documents with their line managers out of fear of forfeiting a 1% salary increment if they do not comply.

3.2 Formal Documents of Learner's Code of Conduct

All participants confirmed that formal documents, such as the code of conduct for learners, learners' incident reports, school policies, and the SGB constitution, were available in schools. Some participants reported that their schools displayed additional documents, such as the general school rules, SASA 84 of 1996, disciplinary policies, classroom policies, and various other school policies, to combat learners' unruly and ill-disciplined behaviour.

Today, parents, teachers, learners, and other stakeholders perceive schools as places of violence, wars, fights, bullying, gangsters, gun-shooting, stabbing, death, killing, and kidnapping of children (Hlongwane, 2022). Due to these harmful factors, the quality of teaching and learning, as well as the effectiveness of CPD programmes, is highly compromised. At the same time, the safety and security of teachers and learners are not guaranteed within the school premises.

Teachers, parents, and learners are aware that corporal punishment has been abolished and that parents are prohibited from authorising teachers to punish their children (Potgieter et al., 1997). In most cases, teachers employ alternative disciplinary measures as prescribed by the DBE, human rights advocates, scholars, and other discipline management theories with very little or no success. The perception is that there is a complete lack of accountability among teachers in implementing alternative disciplinary measures to curb learners' behaviour. School principals often handle many classroom problems since many teachers eschew taking drastic disciplinary measures against learners for misconduct, fearing they may lose their jobs.

Although many documents on learners' code of conduct and disciplinary measures are available for teachers to implement, learners are aware of their constitutional rights enshrined in the Bill of Rights, Chapter 2 of the country's constitution, and that teachers will not violate their rights or act *ultra vires* to remedy their misbehavior. They are also aware that the chances of being suspended and expelled from school for any serious misconduct or wrongful act are very minimal, as such a decision is solely taken by the Head of Department [HOD] (Oosthuizen et al., 2020). In essence, the root cause of deterioration in the quality of teaching and learning in South African schools is a lack of learner discipline and the disempowerment of teachers from acting against ill-disciplined and unruly learners. Discipline is crucial in schools because it enables a positive learning environment that promotes teacher effectiveness, successful learning, and learner outcomes. Generally, discipline fosters a conducive learning environment that promotes the quality of teaching and learning in schools.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The recommendations of this article are based on the research questions that guided this study. The primary research question was: How can ongoing professional teacher development enhance the declining quality of education in South African schools? All recommendations are based on data gathered from interviews, observations, and document analysis.

For CPTD to influence the quality of teaching and learning in schools, the DBE, as an employer, should design and introduce a mandatory CPTD curriculum compelling all serving teachers to remain lifelong learners until they exit the teaching service. It is recommended that teacher training institutions, in consultation with the Department of Higher Education and Training, initiate CPTD programme in the formal pre-service training curriculum for all teacher trainees as a way of exposing them to how it works. It is further recommended that a renewable five-year certificate be awarded to all teachers upon completion of CPTD curriculum requirements.

The DBE, in collaboration with teacher training institutions, could include CPTD programme in the pre-service teacher training curriculum to help teacher trainees appreciate the value of lifelong learning and continuous professional development for enhancing teacher efficiency and improving education quality. As a motivation, the DBE, in collaboration with TTIs or the responsible institution, could award certificates to all teachers who have completed CPTD programme.

CPTD certificates awarded upon completion of the formal curriculum programme should serve as an additional requirement or prerequisite for the registration of beginner teachers and the accreditation of all serving teachers already in the labour market. Therefore, the DBE, as the employer or school authorities, should provide funds for all teachers to cover registration, tuition, and learning materials for the proposed compulsory study programme. To rekindle teachers' appetite for attending CPTD activities, the employer should provide monetary incentives to encourage them to grow and unleash their full potential and incentivise them to remain with the employer until retirement. In South Africa, this practice aligns with the norm of rewarding employees for the services they provide and the in-service courses they have completed.

In relation to school discipline, learners are aware that their chances of being suspended or expelled from school for serious harm or wrongful acts committed are very minimal, and that such decisions are made by the Head of Department (HOD) at the Provincial level. Unfortunately, this knowledge fuels misconduct and indiscipline in schools. To nurture a tranquil and harmonious school environment that optimises teaching and learning, the DBE should empower teachers to take swift and firm disciplinary measures against any learner found guilty of serious misconduct, followed by both suspension and expulsion from the school within the prescripts of SASA, where circumstances warrant. Since learner discipline is a thorny issue in South Africa and globally, the South African government should revisit suspension and expulsion measures in SASA and amend the constitution in a way that would promote learner discipline and school order. To ensure effective learner discipline, the DBE should devolve power and accountability to schools to decide and finalise disciplinary actions, rather than the district director or head of department. However, teachers should implement disciplinary measures in a way that complies with natural justice (*alteram partem*), which

asserts that the culprit should be afforded a fair opportunity to present their version of the case (Oosthuizen et al., 2020).

A lack of educational resources, such as textbooks, laboratory equipment, computers, and other instructional materials, negatively impacts teaching and learning. Therefore, the DBE should procure and deliver all teaching and learning materials to schools prior to the start of the school calendar year.

Curriculum advisors and SMTs should undertake a training-of-trainers course or engage in rigorous CPTD activities in their areas of specialisation before they can train teachers through in-service training. Workshop organisers should maintain CPTD attendance registers for teachers, curriculum advisors, and members of the SMT who fail to attend the programmes so that they can account to the circuit managers or district directors. CPTD training organisers should maintain attendance registers to identify teachers, curriculum advisors, and SMT advisors who do not attend training, so that they can account to the responsible authorities, such as circuit managers or district directors, for their non-attendance.

It is recommended that teachers be exposed to contemporary training and development methods, such as learning teams, engagement with external consultants, attending accredited courses, peer observation, and online professional conversations. Additionally, using CPD models, including training, cascade, deficit, coaching/mentoring, and community of practice, is also recommended. For teachers to uphold the professional norms and standards, perform their teaching responsibilities effectively, and act ethically, the DBE, in collaboration with the South African Council for Educators (SACE), should modify the conditions and terms of teachers' registration with SACE from the current permanent status to provisional and renewable registration after every five years of teaching and learning assessment.

CONCLUSION

The study explored the influence of CPTD on the quality of teaching and learning in South African schools. It probed participants' views on how CPTD can improve the declining quality of education. To improve the quality of education, different categories of participants emphasised the need for teachers to remain lifelong learners and researchers throughout their teaching careers, until they retire from active service. They expressed dissatisfaction with learners' acts of misconduct and indiscipline, characterising them as barriers to effective teaching and learning in schools. The participants also expressed concerns about inadequate and dilapidated infrastructure, as well as a lack of teaching and learning resources, as they undermine the country's efforts to improve the quality of education. While employer (the DBE), CPTD providers, or school authorities offer some rewards to teachers for completing CPTD programmes, monetary incentives could be used to supplement such rewards to raise teachers' motivation and interest to upskill themselves. Almost all the participants perceived monetary compensation as a vital incentive to motivate teachers to attend CPTD activities. Hence, reasonable salary increments, cash bonuses, transportation reimbursement, study bursaries, promotion opportunities, laptops, iPads, and trophies can also be used as incentives to enhance teachers' effectiveness and competencies and student learning in schools.

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